

Speculation On the Role of Acceleration On Entropy

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An accelerating charge radiates energy proportional to acceleration squared. Work on the charge does not simply accelerate the charge and bound E electric and B magnetic field pieces, but leads to pieces of E and B which are not bound and represent radiation which escapes. We have suggested that this is akin to a thermodynamical situation. If acceleration, however, tends to zero, there is virtually no radiation and the usual conservative force Newtonian mechanics appears. (Even with acceleration, the amount of radiation is so low that one often ignores the effect entirely.) We suggest that there seems to be a correlation between acceleration and entropy and investigate an ideal gas under acceleration.

The first example, we consider is a gas which has a large mass against one wall which is sitting on a frictionless surface. This wall is detached from the rest of the container and there is acceleration in the gas which accelerates the mass. We argue that there needs to exist a function $S(T,V)$ such that: $dE = TdS - PdV$ may be used to analyze the problem quasistatically from an initial point to a final. The second example is the well-known free expansion of a gas, for which $\Delta E = \Delta Q + \Delta W$ where all three deltas are 0. Again there is acceleration and so one does not deal with exact T,V equilibrium states, but if one wishes to move from the initial points to the endpoints, one must again postulate a function $S(T,V)$ such that $dE = TdS - PdV$, i.e. one uses a quasistatic path such that the system is always almost in equilibrium. In this case, one may show that dS/dV partial = NR/V . Thus, we argue that entropy plays the role of a function in a quasistatic picture which accounts for the effects of acceleration which upset equilibrium.

Accelerating Charge

It is well known that an accelerating charge radiates with power proportional to acceleration squared. Work done trying to accelerate a charge and the electric $E(v)$ and magnetic $B(v)$ fields bound to the charge also transfers energy to the environment as radiation. This radiation is also associated with E and B field pieces. In other words, solving Maxwell's em equations using retarded time (see (1) pp 458-59) leads to E and B fields which have pieces which drop differently with respect to r than in the usual bound scenario. For example, E may have terms which drop as $1/(r^2)$ and other terms which drop as $1/r$. If one calculates momentum flux $C_1 E \times B$, and integrates grad dot ($C_1 E \times B$) over a sphere surface, the $1/r$ E and B pieces yield momentum flux which leaves the system.

As a particle accelerates it has a $v(t)$ and a $dv(t)/dt$. A bound charge with $v(t)$ and $dv/dt=0$, has $E(v)$ and $B(v)$ which differ from $E(v), B(v)$ for an accelerating charge. In other words, the acceleration appears in the field expressions (linearly). Thus, one physically sees the acceleration, so to speak, in the accelerating E, B field case. It is this acceleration which leads to radiation which we describe as akin to entropy production. In the usual Newtonian picture, one does not see acceleration as kinetic energy is $.5mv^2$ in each dx.

In the next section we wish to examine the effects of acceleration and their relationship to entropy in an ideal gas.

Acceleration in an Ideal Gas

An ideal gas is described by N particles in a container with:

$$E \text{ (energy)} = \frac{3}{2} NRT \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad PV = NRT \quad ((1b))$$

We use E from now on to represent energy. P is pressure and T temperature. Imagine a quasistatic situation in which one wall is not attached, but there exists a force F equal to PA_{Area} holding it in place. One may let the gas expand in tiny steps such that it forms an equilibrium after every step. This is the definition of a quasistatic process. We argue that this really means one removes acceleration. Normally, with symmetry breaking (with the one wall), there should be some acceleration of particles toward the moving wall.

If one has a quasistatic process, the usual Newtonian idea of change in energy = work applies, i.e.

$$dE = \frac{3}{2} NR dT = NRT/V dV \quad ((2))$$

This governs how dT must change with dV , but the quasistatic scenario is somewhat artificial as it is a highly constrained one which stops acceleration to a large degree. This is like the case of a charge which accelerates so slowly that it is almost not accelerating.

We next try to consider two more realistic pictures. First, we consider a large mass M sitting against the free wall and lying on a frictional surface. The gas will push against this mass and accelerate it. If the mass is very large, this acceleration should be small. Nevertheless the situation is no longer quasistatic, but:

$$\Delta E = \Delta \text{Work} \quad ((3))$$

In this case, $\text{Work} = .5M v^2$, the nonrelativistic kinetic energy of the mass. If the mass moves and accelerates slowly, we suggest that $E = \frac{3}{2} NRT$ still roughly holds, but $PV = nRT$ is not the picture because there is some free motion (acceleration) of gas particles in the container due to the pressure and the asymmetry of the free wall. We write the approximate equation:

$$\frac{3}{2} NR T_0 = \frac{3}{2} NRT + .5Mv^2 \quad \text{and note that } v = dV/dt (1/\text{Area of wall}) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Taking } d/dt \text{ yields: } 0 = \frac{3}{2} NR dT/dt + Mv dv/dt \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{If one uses: } PA_{\text{Area}} = M dv/dt \text{ then } ((5)) \text{ becomes: } 0 = \frac{3}{2} dT + dV T \quad ((6))$$

$((6))$, however, is identical to $((2))$, the quasistatic picture. This occurs because one uses P as the force which implies there is no acceleration in the gas, but that it is in an equilibrium state.

This is not the physical situation, but it is fine for the quasistatic picture of ((2)). Thus, we suggest that Mdv/dt is not $P \text{Area}$. As a consequence, the relationship between dV and dT is not that of ((2)) and an initial state of T_0, V_0 changes to T_1, V_1 which differs from the result T_1, V for ((2)).

One may next try to find a quasistatic scenario moving from T_0, V_0 to T_1, V_1 such that the gas is always in equilibrium. This, however, cannot be based on $dE = -PdV$ which is identical to ((2)). Thus, we suggest that a new function $S(T, V)$ must be added such that:

$$dE = TdS - PdV \quad (\text{where } T \text{ is inserted for convenience}) \quad ((7))$$

This TdS plays the role of describing what would normally be the effects of acceleration in a partial free expansion. In thermodynamics, S is called entropy and so we argue that entropy is directly linked to the notion of acceleration. In fact, if one removes acceleration as in the quasistatic $dE = d\text{Work}$ case of ((2)), then $dE = -PdV$.

We next consider a more familiar example, that of free expansion, i.e. the mass M is removed and the free wall may move without any impedance. Again, there is acceleration of the gas particles. Given that no work is done and no heat enters or leaves the gas, one has:

$$\Delta E = \Delta Q + \Delta W \quad ((8))$$

Note: Δ is not the differential d of calculus.

In such a gas, temperature remains unchanged in the initial and final states and so does E . The gas changes from T_0, V_0 , to T_0, V_2 .

One may again ask: What quasistatic scenario may be used to calculate the state variables at T_0, V_2 ? Again, the idea of using quasistatic variable is to remove acceleration by absorbing its effects within a new function $S(T, V)$. One cannot use $dE = -PdV$ because dE is 0. In the free expansion case, there is no work, but in the quasistatic one, there must be because P of the gas is pushing against a matching P on the outside of the wall as the volume changes slightly. Thus, to have $dE=0$, one needs to add an extra function such that:

$$dE = TdS - PdV \quad ((9)) \quad \text{Here } T \text{ is inserted for convenience.}$$

In the free expansion case, one may calculate dS/dV partial because $dE=0$ i.e.

$$T \frac{dS}{dV} \text{ partial} = P \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{dS}{dV} \text{ partial} = NR/V \quad ((10))$$

If the general equation ((9)) holds, the quasistatic example of ((2)) means that $dS=0$. In the next section we show that this is the case.

The Sackur-Tetrode Equation and $dE = -PdV$

A full expression for $S(T, V)$ for an ideal gas is given by the Sackur-Tetrode equation (2):

$S/NR = \ln(V [T \text{ power } 1.5] + C2) \quad ((11))$ where $C2$ is a constant

Using $dS=0$ leads to: $-dV/T = V^{3/2} dT$ which matches ((2))

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that it is acceleration which makes a charged system radiate and this is a thermodynamic type situation because work on the charge/bound fields system does not just lead to kinetic energy, but radiated energy in the environment. Calculating E and B fields using Maxwell's equations and retarded time allows one to see pieces of E and B directly associated with acceleration. These lead to energy pieces which are not part of the kinetic energy of the fields. Thus, there seems to be an association between entropy and acceleration.

We consider the case of an ideal gas for which $E=3/2 NRT$ and $PV=NRT$ and examine partial free expansion (expansion against a large mass M) and free expansion. In both of these cases, we argue that acceleration exists and that the idea of introducing an entropy function is to capture the effects of acceleration while considering a quasistatic process. Such a situation leads to: $dE = TdS - PdV$. Thus, even though ΔE may equal ΔW as it does in both of these cases, a quasistatic picture requires an extra TdS function to account for different dT function of dV scenarios. For example, in the free expansion case, ΔE and ΔW are 0, and dE must also be zero in a quasistatic picture. $-PdV$, however, is not 0 because one must have an outside pressure balancing P of the gas, and if dV occurs, work is necessarily done. In the $dE=0$ case, with $-PdV$ being 0, one must have a new function TdS to balance PdV . This function captures the effects of acceleration which occurs in the physical process (expansion). One may note that acceleration breaks the sense of an equilibrium state and so one wishes to find a quasistatic path for which the system is always in equilibrium.

References

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